

SORSE Workshops: FAIR4RS

19 November 2020

Session 2 Breakout Room 1 Notes

Title: What does interoperability mean for software?

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Participants: all

[IEEE Standard Glossary of Software Engineering Terminology](#)

ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged

[Semantic interoperability](#)

that these exchanges make sense – that the requester and the provider have a common understanding of the ‘meanings’ of the requested services and data.

We should also consider syntactic interoperability (systems exchanged information where what matters is to have shared formats)

Q1: What software interoperability does/should not cover?

Normally interoperability in the software development context is about different pieces of software working together, but it is a high requirement (in my opinion) for the FAIR principles so in that sense it shouldn't cover this definition <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interoperability>

Interoperability within the same software is very dynamic. I feel this would be out of scope. For interacting with other software, APIs should define the input/output or protocol.

Interoperability should not constrain the technical requirements, but rather define standards

Interoperability should not include legal interoperability (which should be under reusability, to keep it with other license related aspects)

Interoperability shouldn't be considered to cover user interaction.

Q2: What would be a working definition of Interoperability for software?

“One piece of software can interact (pass data and instructions) with another, through machine readable descriptions”

Software interoperability should consider different levels: system, syntactic and semantic interoperability.

Q3: What is the single most important element of interoperability for software? Which part of interoperability should we follow?

In the spirit of FAIR principles, the most important element of interoperability is the ability of two pieces of software to communicate without need of modification of either one (neither one needs to adjust to the other, they share a common format/contract/API)

That APIs published and data formats used by the software are described in an open and machine interpretable way.

Shared interfaces and shared (meta)data standards (covering both formats and semantics) between software.

Metadata exchange

Q4: What software interoperability does/should cover?

Interoperability should cover computational resource interoperability e.g. usage of MPI communicators and thread pools.

Open (domain-specific) data format standards

Best practices for software (can apply to other **FAIR** principles)

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_Package_Data_Exchange

Transcribed comments:

<standards>

- LJ Garcia: What sort of standards? An answer to it could be interesting for the newly created Q4

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_Package_Data_Exchange>

- Neil CHue Hong: SPDX is great - I wonder if it is more sensible to be considered part of reusability